

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-300-ODH-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	2	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 300
Injection Volume:	20.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	50.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/29/2023 10:10:49 AM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 10:23:52 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.539	249675	28.96	20011
2	9.369	248647	28.85	18161
3	11.537	182412	21.16	10944
4	15.439	181272	21.03	8295

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-301-ODH-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	120	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 301
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/30/2023 4:50:05 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 10:28:46 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.107	3884327	97.78	357961
2	8.880	2284	0.06	328
3	10.795	78234	1.97	5687
4	14.758	7706	0.19	-276